

GENERALIZED HYERS-ULAM-RASSIAS TYPE STABILITY OF FUNCTIONAL EQUATION DERIVING FROM QUADRATIC MAPPING IN NON-ARCHIMDEAN (l, β) -NORMED SPACE

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we study to solve the Hyers – Ulam – Rassias stability of functional equation deriving from mapping quadratic in Non – Archimdean (l, β) -normed space. Then I will show that the solutions of equation are quadratic mapping. These are the main results of this paper.

Keywords: non-Archimdean (n, β) -normed space Hyers-Ulam-Rassias stability, functional equation deriving from quadratic mapping.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 39B82, 39B72

1. INTRODUCTION

Let $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$ be a normed spaces on the same field $\mathbb{K}$, and $f : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ be a mapping. We use the notation $\|\cdot\|_{\beta_1}$ ($\|\cdot\|_{\beta}$) for corresponding the norms on $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$. In this paper, we investigate the stability of functional equation deriving quadratic from mappimng non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space. In fact, when $\mathbf{X}$ is a non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space with norm $\|\cdot\|_{\beta_1}$ and that $\mathbf{Y}$ is a Banach non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space with norm with norm $\|\cdot\|_{\beta}$

We solve and prove the *Hyers – Ulam – Rassias* type stability of functional equation deriving from mapping quadratic in non-Archimdean (l, β) -normed space, associated to the quadratic functional equation.

$$f\left(\frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} + \sum_{j=1}^k x_j\right) + f\left(\frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} - \sum_{j=1}^k x_j\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(\frac{x_{k+1}}{k}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f(x_j) = 0, \quad (1.1)$$

The study of the functional equation stability originated from a question of S.M. Ulam [24], concerning the stability of group homomorphisms. Let $(\mathbf{G}, *)$ be a group and let $(\mathbf{G}', \circ, d)$ be a metric group with metric $d(\cdot, \cdot)$. Geven $\epsilon > 0$, does there exist a $\delta > 0$

such that if $f : \mathbf{G} \rightarrow \mathbf{G}'$ satisfies

$$d\left(f(x * y), f(x) \circ f(y)\right) < \delta$$

for all $x, y \in \mathbf{G}$ then there is a homomorphism $h : \mathbf{G} \rightarrow \mathbf{G}'$ with

$$d\left(f(x), h(x)\right) < \epsilon$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{G}$?, if the answer, is affirmative, we would say that equation of homomorphism $h(x * y) = h(x) \circ h(y)$ is stable. The concept of stability for a functional equation arises when we replace functional equation by an inequality which acts as a perturbation of the equation. Thus the stability question of functional equations is that how do the solutions of the inequality differ from those of the given function equation?

The Hyers [8] gave firsts affirmative partial answer to the equation of *Ulam* in *Banach* spaces.

Next The stability of quadratic functional equation was proved by Skof [23] for mappings $f : E_1 \rightarrow E_2$ where E_1 is a normed space and E_2 is a Banach space . Cholewa [5] noticed that the theorem of Skof is still true if the relevant domain E_1 is replaced by an Abelian group. The functional equation:

$$f(x + y) + f(x - y) - 2f(x) - 2f(y)$$

is called the quadratic functional equation.

The functional equation:

$$f\left(\frac{x + y}{2}\right) + f\left(\frac{x - y}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{2}f(x) - \frac{1}{2}f(y) = 0$$

is called a Jensen type the quadratic functional equation.

The first work on the stability problem for functional equations in non-Archimedean spaces was started by Moslehian and Rassias [11]. Moslehian and Sadeghi [10] investigated the stability of cubi functional equations in non-Archimedean normed space. Next the mathematicians Xiuzhog Yang, Yachai lui, and Nazek Alessa set up the quadratic equation in non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space

Recently, in [3, 9, 25] the authors studied the Hyers-Ulam-Rassias stability for the following quadratic functional equation in non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space:

$$f(x + 2y) + f(x - 2y) = 4f(x + y) + 4f(x - y) - 6f(x) + f(2y) + f(-2y) - 4f(y) - 4f(-y) \tag{1.2}$$

$$\sum_{1 \leq i \leq j \leq l} \phi(v_i + v_j) + \sum_{1 \leq i \leq j \leq l} \phi(v_i - v_j) = 2(l - 1) \sum_{1 \leq i \leq l} \phi(v_i) \tag{1.3}$$

In this paper, we solve and proved the Hyers-Ulam-Rassias type stability for quadratic functional equation (1.1), ie the quadratic functional equation with $2k$ -variables . Under suitable assumptions on spaces $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$, we will prove that the mappings satisfying the quadratic functional equation (1.1). Thus, the results in this paper are generalization of

those in [3, 9, 25] for quadratic functional equation with $2k - variables$.

The paper is organized as follows:

In section preliminaries we remind some basic some basic properties about in non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space in [10, 11, 25] such as We only redefine the solution definition of the quadratic equation function.

Section 3: is devoted to prove the Hyers-Ulam stability of the quadratic functional equation (1.1) when when $\mathbf{X}$ is a non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space with norm $\|\cdot\|_{\beta_1}$ and that $\mathbf{Y}$ is a Banach non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space with norm with norm $\|\cdot\|_{\beta}$

2. PRELIMINARIES

2.1. (n, β) -normed spaces.

Definition 2.1.

Let $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in a normed space $\mathbf{X}$.

- (1) A sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ in a space $\mathbf{X}$ is a Cauchy sequence iff the sequence $\{x_{n+1} - x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ converges to zero.
- (2) The sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is said to be convergent if, for any $\epsilon > 0$, there are a positive integer N and $x \in \mathbf{X}$ such that

$$\|x_n - x\| \leq \epsilon, \forall n \geq N,$$

for all $n, m \geq N$. Then the point $x \in \mathbf{X}$ is called the limit of sequence x_n and denote $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$.

- (3) If every sequence Cauchy in $\mathbf{X}$ converges, then the normed space $\mathbf{X}$ is called a Banach space.

Definition 2.2.

Let $\mathbf{X}$ be a linear space over $\mathbb{R}$ with $\dim \mathbf{X} \geq n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 < \beta \leq 1$ let $\|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\| : \mathbf{X}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. be a function satisfying the following properties:

- (1) $\|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_{\beta} = 0$ if and only if $x_1, \dots, x_n$ are linearly dependent,
- (2) $\|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_{\beta}$ is invariant under permutations of $x_1, \dots, x_n$
- (3) $\|\alpha x_1, \dots, x_n\|_{\beta} = |\alpha|^{\beta} \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|$
- (4) $\|x_1, \dots, x_n, y + z\|_{\beta} \leq \|x_1, \dots, x_n, y\|_{\beta} + \|x_1, \dots, x_n, z\|_{\beta}, \forall x_1, \dots, x_n, y, z \in \mathbf{X}$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. Then the function $\|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|$ is called an (n, β) -norm on $\mathbf{X}$ and the pair $(\mathbf{X}, \|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|)$ is called a linear (n, β) -normed space or an (n, β) -normed space.

* Note that the concept of a linear (n, β) -normed space is a generalization of a linear n -normed space ($\beta = 1$) and of a linear n -normed space ($n = 1$)

Definition 2.3.

A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a linear (n, β) -normed space $\mathbf{X}$ is called a convergent sequence if there is $x \in \mathbf{X}$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1}\|_\beta = 0$ for all $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1} \in \mathbf{X}$. *Note we call that $\{x_n\}$ convergent to x or that x is the limit of $\{x_n\}$, witer $\{x_n\} \rightarrow x$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ or $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$.

Definition 2.4.

A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a linear (n, β) -normed space $\mathbf{X}$ is called a Cauchy sequence if $\lim_{n, m \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x_m, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1}\|_\beta = 0$ for all $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1} \in \mathbf{X}$.

Definition 2.5.

A linear (n, β) -normed space in which every Cauchy sequence is convergent is called a complete (n, β) -normed space.

2.2. The properties of (n, β) -normed spaces.

Lemma 2.6.

Let $(\mathbf{X}, \|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|_\beta)$ be a linear (n, β) -normed space, $k \geq 1, 0 < \beta \leq 1$. If $x_1 \in \mathbf{X}$ and $\|x_1, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1}\|_\beta = 0$ for all $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1} \in \mathbf{X}$, then $x_1 = 0$.

Lemma 2.7.

For a convergent sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a linear (n, β) -normed space $\mathbf{X}$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1}\|_\beta = \|\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1}\|_\beta = 0$$

for all $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1} \in \mathbf{X}$.

2.3. non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed spaces. In this subsection we recall some basic notations from [9,10] such as non-Archimedean fields, non-Archimedean normed spaces and non-Archimedean Banach spaces.

A valuation is a function $|\cdot|$ from a field $\mathbb{K}$ into $[0, \infty)$ such that 0 is the unique element having the 0 valuation,

$$\begin{aligned} |r| &= 0 \Leftrightarrow r = 0 \\ |r \cdot s| &:= |r| |s|, \forall r, s \in \mathbb{K} \end{aligned}$$

and the triangle inequality holds, i.e.,

$$|r + s| \leq |r| + |s|, \forall r, s \in \mathbb{K}.$$

A field $\mathbb{K}$ is called a valued field if $\mathbb{K}$ carries a valuation. The usual absolute values of $\mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbb{C}$ are examples of valuation. Let us consider a valuation which satisfies a stronger condition than the triangle inequality. If the strong triangle inequality is replaced by

$$|r + s| \leq \max\{|r|, |s|\}, \forall r, s \in \mathbb{K},$$

then the function $|\cdot|$ is called a non-Archimedean valuation. Clearly, $|1| = |-1| = 1$ and $|n| \leq 1, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. A trivial example of a non-Archimedean valuation is the function

$|\cdot|$ talking everything except for 0 into 1 and $|0| = 0$. In this paper, we assume that the base field is a non-Archimedean field with $|2| \neq 1$, hence call it simply a field.

Definition 2.8. Let X be a vector space over a field $\mathbb{K}$ with a non-Archimedean valuation $|\cdot|$. A function $\|\cdot\| : X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is said a non-Archimedean norm if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (1) $\|x\| = 0$ if and only if $x = 0$;
- (2) $\|rx\| = |r|\|x\|$ ($r \in \mathbb{K}, x \in X$);
- (3) $\|x + y\| \leq \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\}$ $x, y \in X$ hold.

Then $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is called a norm-Archimedean norm space.

Definition 2.9.

A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a norm-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space $\mathbf{X}$ is a Cauchy sequence if and only if $\{x_n - x_m\} \rightarrow 0$.

Definition 2.10. Let $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in a norm-Archimedean normed space X .

- (1) A sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ in a non-Archimedean space is a Cauchy sequence iff the sequence $\{x_{n+1} - x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ converges to zero.
- (2) The sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to be convergent if, for any $\epsilon > 0$, there are a positive integer N and $x \in X$ such that

$$\|x_n - x\| \leq \epsilon, \forall n \geq N,$$

for all $n, m \geq N$. Then we call $x \in X$ a limit of sequence x_n and denote $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$.

- (3) If every sequence Cauchy in X converges, then the norm-Archimedean normed space X is called a norm-Archimedean Banach space.

Definition 2.11.

Let $\mathbf{X}$ be a real space with $\dim \mathbf{X} \geq n$ over a scalar field $\mathbb{K}$ with a non-Archimedean nontrivial valuation $|\cdot|$, where n is a positive integer and β is a constant with $0 < \beta \leq 1$. A real-valued function let $\|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\| : \mathbf{X}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. is called an (n, β) -norm on $\mathbf{X}$ satisfying the following properties:

- (1) $\|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_{\beta} = 0$ if and only if $x_1, \dots, x_n$ are linearly dependent,

- (2) $\|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_\beta$ is invariant under permutations of $x_1, \dots, x_n$
- (3) $\|\alpha x_1, \dots, x_n\|_\beta = |\alpha|^\beta \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_\beta$
- (4) $\|x_0 + x_1, \dots, x_n\|_\beta \leq \max\{\|x_0, \dots, x_n\|_\beta, \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|_\beta\}, \forall x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbf{X}$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{K}$. Then the function $\|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|_\beta$ is called an (n, β) -norm on $\mathbf{X}$ and the pair $(\mathbf{X}, \|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|_\beta)$ is called a non -Archimedean (n, β) -normed space or an (n, β) -normed space.

* Note that the concept of a non -Archimedean (n, β) -normed space is a non -Archimedean n -normed space if $(\beta = 1)$ and a a non -Archimedean β -normed space if $n=1$ respectively.

2.4. **Solutions of the equation.** The functional equation

$$f(x + y) + f(x - y) = 2f(x) + 2f(y)$$

is called the quadratic equation. In particular, every solution of the quadratic equation is said to be an *quadratic mapping*.

3. STABILITY RESULTS.

Here, we consider $|k| \neq 1$ and examine the Hyers-Ulam stability of the functional equation (1.1) when when $\mathbf{X}$ is a non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space with norm $\|\cdot\|_{\beta_1}$ and that $\mathbf{Y}$ is a Banach non-Archimedean (n, β) -normed space with norm with norm $\|\cdot\|_\beta$ Under this setting, we can show that the mapping satisfying (1.1) is quadratic. These results are give in the following.

Theorem 3.1.

Suppose That $\mathbf{X}$ is a non-Archimedean β_1 -normed space and that $\mathbf{Y}$ is a complete non-Archimedean (l, β) -normed space, where $l \geq 2$, $0 < \beta, \beta_1 \leq 1$. Let $\epsilon \in [0, \infty)$, $p \in (0, \infty)$ with $\beta_1 p > \beta$ and let

$$\varphi : \mathbf{Y}^{l-1} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

be a function. Suppose that a mapping

$$f: \mathbf{X}^{2k} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying $f(0) = 0$ and the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f(x_j) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \epsilon \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \|x_j\|_{\beta_1}^p + \sum_{j=1}^k \|x_{k+j}\|_{\beta_1}^p \right) \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Then there exists a unique quadratic mapping

$$H : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying

$$\left\| f(x) - H(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon k \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.2)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$.

Proof. Replace $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k, x_{k+1}, x_{k+2}, \dots, x_{2k})$ by $(x, x, \dots, x, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$ we have

$$\left\| 2f(kx) - 2kf(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.3)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$

and dividing both sides by $\left| (2k)^{\beta} \right|$, we get

$$\left\| \frac{f(kx)}{k} - f(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.4)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Replacing x by $k^n x$ in (3.4)

and dividing both sides by $\left| k^{n\beta} \right|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \frac{f(k^{n+1}x)}{k^{n+1}} - \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| \frac{1}{k^{n\beta}} \right| \left| \frac{1}{(2k)^{\beta}} \right| \left| k^{n\beta_1 p} \right| \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \\ & = \epsilon \cdot k \left| \frac{1}{(2k)^{\beta}} \right| \left| k^{(\beta_1 p - \beta)} \right|^n \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Since $p\beta_1 > \beta$ and $|k| \neq 1$, we obtain that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| \frac{f(k^{n+1}x)}{k^{n+1}} - \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$

. It follows from (3.6) that the sequence $\left\{ \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n} \right\}$ is Cauchy sequence for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. Since $\mathbf{Y}$ is complete space, the sequence $\left\{ \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n} \right\}$ converges. So one can define the mapping $H: \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ by

$$H(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n} \quad (3.7)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$.

It follows from (3.1) and (3.7) and lemma 2.7 that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| H \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} \right) + H \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} \right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H \left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k} \right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| k^{-n\beta} \left[f \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} \right) + H \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f \left(k^n x_j \right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f \left(k^n \frac{x_{k+j}}{k} \right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \epsilon \left\| k^{-n\beta} \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \left\| k^n x_j \right\|_{\beta_1}^p + \sum_{j=1}^k \left\| k^n x_{k+j} \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \right) \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \right\| \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \epsilon \left\| k^{n(\beta_1 p - \beta)} \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \left\| k^n x_j \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \right) \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \right\| \end{aligned}$$

and so for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Since $p\beta_1 > \beta$ and $|k| \neq 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| H \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} \right) + H \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j} \right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H \left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k} \right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By lemma 2.6, we get

$$H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) = 0$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. So mapping H is quadratic.

replace x by kx in (3.3) and dividing both sides by $\left|(2k^2)^\beta\right|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \frac{f(k^2x)}{k^2} - \frac{f(kx)}{k}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \\ & \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| (2k^2)^{-\beta} \right| \left\| kx \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Thus, by(3.3) and (3.8)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f(x) - \frac{f(k^2x)}{k^2}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \left\| \frac{f(kx)}{k} - f(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta, \left\| \frac{f(k^2x)}{k^2} - \frac{f(kx)}{k}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \right\} \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \epsilon \cdot k \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}), \epsilon \cdot k \left| (2k^2)^{-\beta} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Since $p\beta_1 > \beta$ and $|k| \neq 1$, we obtain

$$\left\| f(x) - \frac{f(k^2x)}{k^2}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{-2\beta} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.10)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By induction on n , we can conclude that

$$\left\| f(x) - \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.11)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Replacing x by kx in (3.11)

and dividing both sides by $\left|k^\beta\right|$, we get

$$\left\| \frac{f(kx)}{k} - \frac{f(k^{n+1}x)}{k^{n+1}}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \left| k^{-\beta} \right| \left\| kx \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.12)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. It follow from (3.3) and (3.12)

$$\left\| f(x) - \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{-2\beta} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.13)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Passing the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ (3.11), we can get (3.2) Next, we prove the uniqueness of H . Assume that $H_1 : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ is an additive mapping satisfying (3.2). Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| H(x) - H_1(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &= \left| k^{-n\beta} \right| \left\| H(k^n x) - H_1(k^n x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &\leq \left| k^{-n\beta} \right| \max \left\{ \left\| H(k^n x) - f(k^n x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta}, \right. \\ & \left. \left\| f(k^n x) - H_1(k^n x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\} \\ &\leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{-n\beta} \right| \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \left\| k^n x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \\ &= \epsilon \cdot k^{kq\beta_1} \left| k^{p\beta_1 - \beta} \right|^n \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\left\| H(x) - H_1(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} = 0$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By lemma 2.6, we get $H(x) = H_1(x)$ for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. So H is the unique additive mapping satisfying (3.2) Let

□

Theorem 3.2.

Suppose That $\mathbf{X}$ is a non-Archimedean β_1 -normed space and that $\mathbf{Y}$ is a complete non-Archimedean (l, β) -normed space, where $l \geq 2$, $0 < \beta, \beta_1 \leq 1$. Let $\epsilon \in [0, \infty)$, $p \in (0, \infty)$ with $\beta_1 p < \beta$ and let

$$\varphi : \mathbf{Y}^{l-1} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

be a function. Suppose that a mapping

$$f : \mathbf{X}^{2k} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying $f(0) = 0$ and the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f(x_j) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \epsilon \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \|x_j\|_{\beta_1}^p + \sum_{j=1}^k \|x_{k+j}\|_{\beta_1}^p \right) \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Then there exists a unique additive mapping

$$H : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying

$$\left\| f(x) - H(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon k |k^{-\beta}| \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.16)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$.

Proof. Put $x_j = x$ and $x_{k+j} = 0$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ in (3.15), we get

$$\left\| 2f(kx) - 2kf(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.17)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$ replace x by $\frac{x}{k}$ and dividing both sides by $|2^\beta|$ in (3.17) we get we get

$$\left\| f(x) - kf\left(\frac{x}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot |2^{-\beta}| k |k^{-p\beta_1}| \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.18)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Replacing x by $\frac{x}{k^n}$ in (3.18)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| k^n f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right) - k^{n+1} f\left(\frac{x}{k^{n+1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \epsilon |2^{-\beta}| \cdot k |k^{n\beta}| |k^{-p\beta_1}| |k^{-n\beta_1 p}| \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \\ & = \epsilon |2^{-\beta}| \cdot k |k^{n\beta}| |k^{-\beta_1 p(n+1)}| \|x\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Since $p\beta_1 < \beta$ and $|k| \neq 1$, we obtain that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| k^{n+1} f\left(\frac{x}{k^{n+1}}\right) - k^n f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} = 0 \quad (3.20)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$

. It follows from (3.20) that the sequence $\left\{k^n f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right)\right\}$ is Cauchy sequence for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. Since $\mathbf{Y}$ is complete space, the sequence $\left\{k^n f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right)\right\}$ converges. So one can define the mapping $H: \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ by

$$H(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} k^n f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right) \tag{3.21}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$.

It follows from (3.15) and (3.21) and lemma 2.7 that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{n\beta} \right| \left\| f\left[k^{-n} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^n x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right)\right] \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(k^{-n} x_j\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(k^{-n} \frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \epsilon \left| k^{n\beta} \right| \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \left\| k^{-n} x_j \right\|_{\beta_1}^p + \sum_{j=1}^k \left\| k^{-n} x_{k+j} \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \right) \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \epsilon \left| k^{(\beta-\beta_1 p)n} \right| \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \left\| x_j \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \right) \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned}$$

and so for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Since $p\beta_1 < \beta$ and $|k| \neq 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By lemma 2.6, we get

$$H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) = 0$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. So mapping H is quadratic.

replace x by $\frac{x}{k}$ in (3.18) and multiplying both sides by $|k^\beta|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| k^2 f\left(\frac{x}{k^2}\right) - kf\left(\frac{x}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \epsilon k \left| 2^{-\beta} \right| \cdot \left| k^{\beta} \right| \left\| \frac{x}{k} \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

Thus, by (3.17) and (3.22)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f(x) - k^2 f\left(\frac{x}{k^2}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \left\| kf\left(\frac{x}{k}\right) - f(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta}, \left\| k^2 f\left(\frac{x}{k^2}\right) - kf\left(\frac{x}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\} \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \epsilon k \cdot |2^{-\beta}| \left\| \frac{x}{k} \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}), \epsilon k \cdot |2^{-\beta}| \left| k^{2\beta} \right| \left\| \frac{x}{k^2} \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

Since $p\beta_1 < \beta$ and $|k| \neq 1$, we obtain

$$\left\| f(x) - k^2 f\left(\frac{x}{k^2}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{-p\beta_1} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.24)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By induction on n , we can conclude that

$$\left\| f(x) - k^n f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{-2\beta} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.25)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Replacing x by $\frac{x}{k}$ in (3.11)

and multiplying both sides by $|k^{\beta}|$, we get

$$\left\| kf\left(\frac{x}{k}\right) - k^{n+1} f\left(\frac{x}{k^{n+1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{\beta} \right| \left| k^{-p\beta_1} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.26)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. It follow from (3.17) and (3.43)

$$\left\| f(x) - k^{n+1} f\left(\frac{x}{k^{n+1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{-p\beta_1} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.27)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, n \in \mathbb{N}$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Passing the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ (3.59), we can get (3.16) Next, we prove the uniqueness of H . Assume that $H_1 : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ is an additive

mapping satisfying (3.16). Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left\| H(x) - H_1(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
 &= \left| k^{n\beta} \right| \left\| H\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right) - H_1\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
 &\leq \left| k^{n\beta} \right| \max \left\{ \left\| H\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right) - f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta}, \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left\| f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right) - H_1\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\} \\
 &\leq \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{n\beta} \right| \left| k^{-p\beta_1} \right| \left\| \frac{x}{k^n} \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \\
 &= \epsilon \cdot k \left| k^{\beta-p\beta_1} \right|^n \left| k^{-p\beta_1} \right| \left\| x \right\|_{\beta_1}^p \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \tag{3.28}
 \end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\left\| H(x) - H_1(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} = 0$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By lemma (1.4), we get $H(x) = H_1(x)$ for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. So H is the unique additive mapping satisfying (3.16) Let

□

Theorem 3.3.

Suppose That $\mathbf{X}$ be a vector space and that $\mathbf{Y}$ is a complete non-Archimedean (l, β) -normed space, where $l \geq 2$, $0 < \beta \leq 1$. Let

$$\varphi : \mathbf{X}^{2k} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

be a function such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{1}{k^{n\beta}} \right| \varphi\left(k^n x_1, k^n x_2, \dots, k^n x_k, k^n x_{k+1}, k^n x_{k+2}, \dots, k^n x_{2k}\right) = 0 \tag{3.29}$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$, and

suppose that a mapping

$$\psi : \mathbf{Y}^{l-1} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

be a function. The limit

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{k^{i\beta}} \right| \varphi\left(k^{i-1} x_1, k^{i-1} x_2, \dots, k^{i-1} x_k, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right), 1 \leq i \leq n \right\} \tag{3.30}$$

exists for $x \in \mathbf{X}$, and it is denoted by $\tilde{\varphi}(x)$. Suppose that a mapping

$$f : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying $f(0) = 0$ the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) + f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f(x_j) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k, x_{k+1}, x_{k+2}, \dots, x_{2k}) \cdot \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Then there exists a unique additive mapping

$$H : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying

$$\left\| f(x) - H(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \tilde{\varphi}(x) \varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.32)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Moreover, if

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{k^{i\beta}} \right| \varphi(k^{i-1}x_1, k^{i-1}x_2, \dots, k^{i-1}x_k, 0, 0, \dots, 0), 1 + h \leq i \leq n + h \right\} = 0 \quad (3.33)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$, then H is a unique additive mapping satisfying (3.32).

Proof. Put $x_j = x, x_{k+j} = 0$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ in (3.31) and dividing both sides by $\left| (2k)^\beta \right|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \frac{f(kx)}{k} - f(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \varphi(x, x, \dots, x, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.34)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Replacing x by $k^i x$ in (3.34)

and dividing both sides by $\left| k^{i\beta} \right|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \frac{f(k^{i+1}x)}{k^{i+1}} - \frac{f(k^i x)}{k^i}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \left| (2k)^{-\beta} \right| \left| k^{-i\beta} \right| \varphi(k^i x, k^i x, \dots, k^i x, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.35)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Taking the limit as $i \rightarrow \infty$ and considering (3.29)

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \left\| \frac{f(k^{i+1}x)}{k^{i+1}} - \frac{f(k^i x)}{k^i}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} = 0 \quad (3.36)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$

. It follows from (3.36) that the sequence $\left\{ \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n} \right\}$ is Cauchy sequence for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. Since $\mathbf{Y}$ is complete space, the sequence $\left\{ \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n} \right\}$ converges. So one can define the mapping $H: \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ by

$$H(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n} \quad (3.37)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$.

It follows from (3.31), (3.54) and lemma 1.4 that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{-n\beta} \right| \left\| f\left[k^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right)\right] + f\left[k^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right)\right] - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(k^n x_j\right) \right. \\ & \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(k^n \frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{-n\beta} \right| \varphi(k^n x, k^n x, \dots, k^n x, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned}$$

and so for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Taking the limit as $i \rightarrow \infty$ and considering (3.29) we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) \right. \\ & \left. , z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\| = 0 \end{aligned}$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By lemma 1.4, we get

$$H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) = 0$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. So mapping H is quadratic. Replace x by kx in (3.34) and dividing both sides by $|k^\beta|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \frac{f(k^2x)}{k^2} - \frac{f(kx)}{k}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \\ & \leq \left\| |k^{-2\beta}| \varphi(k^n x, k^n x, \dots, k^n x, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \right\| \end{aligned} \quad (3.38)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Considering (3.34), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f(x) - \frac{f(k^2x)}{k^2}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \left\| |k^{-\beta}| \varphi(x, x, \dots, x, 0, 0, \dots, 0), |k^{-2\beta}| \varphi(kx, kx, \dots, kx, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \right\| \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (3.39)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By induction on n , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f(x) - \frac{f(k^n x)}{k^n}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \frac{\varphi(k^{h-1}x, k^{h-1}x, \dots, k^{h-1}x, 0, 0, \dots, 0)}{|k^{h\beta}|}, 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.40)$$

replacing x by kx in (3.40) and dividing both sides by $|k^\beta|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \frac{f(kx)}{k} - \frac{f(k^{n+1}x)}{k^{n+1}}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_\beta \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \frac{\varphi(k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x, k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x)}{|k^{(h+1)\beta}|}, \right. \\ & \left. 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.41)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, which together with (3.34) implies .

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| f(kx) - \frac{f(k^{n+1}x)}{k^{n+1}}, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
& \leq \max \left\{ \frac{\varphi(x, x, \dots, x, kx, kx, \dots, kx)}{|k^{\beta}|}, \frac{\varphi(k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x, k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x)}{|k^{(h+1)\beta}|} \right. \\
& \left. , 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \\
& = \max \left\{ \frac{\varphi(k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x, k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x)}{|k^{(h+1)\beta}|}, 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \\
& = \max \left\{ \frac{\varphi(k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x, k^h x, k^h x, \dots, k^h x)}{|k^{h\beta}|}, 1 \leq h \leq n+1 \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.42)
\end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$, $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{2k-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. This completes the proof of (3.57) Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.57). Now we need to prove the uniqueness of H . Let H' be another additive mapping satisfying (3.48). Since

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{1}{k^{h\beta}} \right| \tilde{\varphi}(k^h x) &= \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{k^{i\beta}} \right| \varphi(k^{i+h-1} x_1, k^{i+h-1} x_2, \dots, k^{h+i-1} x_k, \right. \\
& \left. k^{h+i-1} k x_{k+1}, k^{h+i-1} x_{k+2}, \dots, k^{h+i-1} x_{2k}), 1 \leq i \leq n \right\} \\
&= \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{k^{i\beta}} \right| \varphi(k^{i-1} x_1, k^{i-1} x_2, \dots, k^{i-1} x_k, \right. \\
& \left. k^{i-1} k x_{k+1}, k^{i-1} x_{k+2}, \dots, k^{i-1} x_{2k}), 1+h \leq i \leq n+h \right\} \quad (3.43)
\end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$, $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$, it follows from then H is a unique additive mapping satisfying (3.49) that.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| H(x) - H'(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
&= \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{1}{k^{h\beta}} \right| \left\| H(k^h x) - H'(k^h x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
&\leq \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{1}{k^{h\beta}} \right| \max \left\{ \left\| H(k^h x) - f(k^h x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta}, \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left\| f(k^h x) - H'(k^h x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\} \\
&\leq \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{1}{k^{h\beta}} \right| \tilde{\varphi}(k^{h\beta} x) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{3.44}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. □

. From lemma 6, we conclude that the quadratic function H is unique.

Theorem 3.4.

Suppose That $\mathbf{X}$ be a vector space and that $\mathbf{Y}$ is a complete non-Archimedean (l, β) -normed space, where $k \geq 1$, $0 < \beta \leq 1$. Let

$$\varphi : \mathbf{X}^{2k} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

be a function such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{n\beta} \right| \varphi \left(\frac{x_1}{k^n}, \frac{x_2}{k^n}, \dots, \frac{x_k}{k^n}, \frac{x_{k+1}}{k^n}, \frac{x_{k+2}}{k^n}, \dots, \frac{x_{2k}}{k^n} \right) = 0 \tag{3.45}$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$, and

suppose that a mapping

$$\psi : \mathbf{Y}^{l-1} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$$

be a function. The limit

$$\tilde{\varphi}(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| k^{(i-1)\beta} \right| \varphi(k^{-i} x, k^{-i} x, \dots, k^{-i} x, 0, 0, \dots, 0), 1 \leq i \leq n \right\} \tag{3.46}$$

exists for $x \in \mathbf{X}$, and it is denoted by $\tilde{\varphi}(x)$. Suppose that a mapping

$$f : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying $f(0) = 0$ the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) + f\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) - 2\sum_{j=1}^k f(x_j) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - 2\sum_{j=1}^k f\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k, x_{k+1}, x_{k+2}, \dots, x_{2k}) \cdot \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.47)$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Then there exists a unique quadratic mapping

$$H : \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$$

satisfying

$$\left\| f(x) - H(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \tilde{\varphi}(x)\varphi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.48)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Moreover, if

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| k^{(i-1)\beta} \left| \varphi(k^{-i}x, k^{-i}x, \dots, k^{-i}x, 0, 0, \dots, 0), 1+h \leq i \leq n+h \right| \right\} = 0 \quad (3.49)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$, then H is a unique additive mapping satisfying (3.48).

Proof. Put $x_j = x, x_{k+j} = 0$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ in (3.47) we get

$$\left\| 2f(kx) - 2kf(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \leq \varphi(x, x, \dots, x, 0, 0, \dots, 0)\psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \quad (3.50)$$

Dividing both sides by $|2^{-\beta}|$ and replace x by $\frac{x}{k}$ in (3.50) we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f(x) - kf\left(\frac{x}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq |2^{-\beta}| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k}, \frac{x}{k}, \dots, \frac{x}{k}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right)\psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.51)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Replacing x by $\frac{x}{k^{i-1}}$ in (3.51)

and multiplying both sides by $|k^{(i-1)\beta}|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| k^i f\left(\frac{x}{k^i}\right) - k^{(i-1)} f\left(\frac{x}{k^{i-1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq |2^{-\beta}| \left| k^{(i-1)\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^i}, \frac{x}{k^i}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^i}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right)\psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.52)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Taking the limit as $i \rightarrow \infty$ and considering (3.45)

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \left\| \left\| k^i f\left(\frac{x}{k^i}\right) - k^{(i-1)} f\left(\frac{x}{k^{i-1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\| = 0 \quad (3.53)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$

. It follows from (3.53) that the sequence $\left\{ k^i f\left(\frac{x}{k^i}\right) \right\}$ is Cauchy sequence for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. Since $\mathbf{Y}$ is complete space, the sequence $\left\{ k^i f\left(\frac{x}{k^i}\right) \right\}$ converges. So one can define the mapping $H: \mathbf{X} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ by

$$H(x) := \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} k^i f\left(\frac{x}{k^i}\right) \quad (3.54)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. It follows from (3.47), (3.53) and lemma 1.4 that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \left\| H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. , z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\| \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| k^{n\beta} \left\| f\left[k^{-n} \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right)\right] + f\left[k^{-n} \left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right)\right] \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(\frac{1}{k^n} x_j\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k f\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k^{n+1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\| \\ &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| k^{n\beta} \left| \varphi(k^{-n}x, k^{-n}x, \dots, k^{-n}x, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \right| \right\| \end{aligned}$$

and so for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and considering (3.45) we get

$$\left\| \left\| H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. , z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\| = 0$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{2k-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By lemma 1.4, we get

$$H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) + H\left(\sum_{j=1}^k x_j - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k x_{k+j}\right) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H(x_j) - 2 \sum_{j=1}^k H\left(\frac{x_{k+j}}{k}\right) = 0$$

for all $x_j, x_{k+j} \in \mathbf{X}$ for all $j = 1 \rightarrow k$. So mapping H is quadratic.

Replace x by $\frac{x}{k}$ in (3.51) and multiplying both sides by $\left| k^{\beta} \right|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| k^2 f\left(\frac{x}{k^2}\right) - k f\left(\frac{x}{k}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq |2^{-\beta}| \left| k^{2\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^2}, \frac{x}{k^2}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.55)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. Considering (3.51), we receive

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f(x) - k^2 f\left(\frac{x}{k^2}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \max \left\{ |2^{-\beta}| \left| k^{\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k}, \frac{x}{k}, \dots, \frac{x}{k}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right), |2^{-\beta}| \left| k^{2\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^2}, \frac{x}{k^2}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right) \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.56)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$, $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. By induction on n , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| f(x) - k^n f\left(\frac{x}{k^n}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \left| k^{(i-1)\beta} \right| \varphi(k^{-i}x, k^{-i}x, \dots, k^{-i}x, 0, 0, \dots, 0) |2^{-\beta}|, 1 \leq i \leq n \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.57)$$

replacing x by $\frac{x}{k}$ in (3.57) and multiplying both sides by $|k^{\beta}|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| k f\left(\frac{x}{k}\right) - k^{n+1} f\left(\frac{x}{k^{n+1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \left| k^{(h+1)\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^h}, \frac{x}{k^h}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^h}, \frac{x}{k^h}, \frac{x}{k^h}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^h}\right), \right. \\ & \left. 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.58)$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$, $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, which together with (3.50) implies .

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| f(x) - f\left(\frac{x}{k^{n+1}}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
& \leq \max \left\{ \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k}, \frac{x}{k}, \dots, \frac{x}{k}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right), \left| k^{(h-1)\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^h}, \frac{x}{k^h}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^h}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right), 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \\
& \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{2k-1}) \\
& \leq \max \left\{ \left| k^{(h-1)\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^h}, \frac{x}{k^h}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^h}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right), 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{2k-1}) \quad (3.59)
\end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$, $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. passing the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.57), we get (3.48). Now we need to prove the quadratic function uniqueness of H . Let H' be another quadratic mapping satisfying (3.48). Sence

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{h\beta} \right| \tilde{\varphi}\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right) &= \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{h\beta} \right| \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| k^{(h-1)\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^h}, \frac{x}{k^h}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^h}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right), 1 \leq h \leq n \right\} \\
&= \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \left| k^{(h-1)\beta} \right| \varphi\left(\frac{x}{k^h}, \frac{x}{k^h}, \dots, \frac{x}{k^h}, 0, 0, \dots, 0\right), 1+h \leq i \leq n+h \right\} \quad (3.60)
\end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$. It follows from (3.49) that.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| H(x) - H'(x), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{2k-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
&= \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{h\beta} \right| \left\| H\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right) - H'\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \\
&\leq \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{h\beta} \right| \max \left\{ \left\| H\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right) - f\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta}, \right. \\
& \left. \left\| f\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right) - H'\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right), z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \right\|_{\beta} \right\} \\
&\leq \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \left| k^{h\beta} \right| \tilde{\varphi}\left(\frac{x}{k^h}\right) \psi(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1}) = 0 \quad (3.61)
\end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in \mathbf{X}$ and $z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{l-1} \in \mathbf{Y}$. □

. From lemma 6, we conclude that the quadratic function H is unique.

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